

POLICY BRIEF

Exploratory Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of Digital Rehabilitation Services

Use of the Inclusion App for Persons with Low Back Pain in Rwanda

Digital rehabilitation offers a promising approach to scale up healthcare services and improve patient access, especially in resource-limited settings. However, despite this potential, there is limited evidence on their real-world cost-effectiveness. This policy brief presents early findings of a study **comparing the costs and quality of life outcomes for patients with low back pain treated with; 1) standard physiotherapy services, versus 2) digital rehabilitation services using the Inclusion App in Rwanda**. These findings provide new evidence to inform healthcare policy discussions on digital rehabilitation services.

THE PROJECT

The **Co-innovation of Digital Rehabilitation in the Global Marketplace (DIRECT) project**, launched in early 2022, seeks to promote evidence-based services, create replicable and scalable digital rehabilitation service models, and address critical healthcare disparities. It is a joint initiative by JAMK University of Applied Sciences, Physiotools Ltd., and CSE Entertainment Ltd., funded by Business Finland. In Rwanda, the University of Rwanda and its Centre of Excellence in Biomedical Engineering and eHealth (CEBE) are the primary implementing partner and local lead.

As part of this effort, Physitrack and Physiotools developed the **Inclusion App** to improve rehabilitation access in underserved regions such as

Rwanda, Indonesia, Kenya, and Tanzania. By leveraging digital solutions, the app empowers physiotherapists and community health workers (CHWs) to deliver scalable, cost-effective care. To date, the program has reached over 15,000 users in these countries.

The Inclusion App is a mobile health solution designed by clinical professionals to be used by the clients themselves. The app provides structured exercise programs that enable CHWs to provide early-phase rehabilitation for common musculoskeletal conditions such as low back pain, neck pain, and arthritis.

WHY LOW BACK PAIN?

Low back pain was selected for analysis because it was **the most prevalent condition among Inclusion App users**, with 51.6% of 6,809 clients used its low back pain exercise programmes. Other frequently used programs included shoulder exercises (17.4%) and hip arthritis (6.2%). This trend aligns with the high global prevalence of low back pain, which affects approximately 70 per 1,000 people, making it the most widespread musculoskeletal disorder [1]. Additionally, low back pain was chosen for analysis because **comparable rehabilitation services exist within Rwanda's public healthcare system**, serving a similar patient group, enabling meaningful cost-effectiveness comparisons.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- ▶ **Scale up digital rehabilitation solutions for persons with low back pain.**
- ▶ **Assess the suitability of digital rehabilitation for other musculoskeletal disorders.**
- ▶ **Explore reimbursement options, tokens or performance-based financing, for digital rehabilitation.**
- ▶ **Develop and implement training programmes for community health workers.**
- ▶ **Integrate digital rehabilitation tools with existing physiotherapy services.**

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PHYSIOTHERAPY PATHWAY

DIGITAL REHABILITATION PATHWAY

Figure 1: Flowchart illustrating the steps and timelines of the two care pathways: 1) Physiotherapy, and 2) Digital Rehabilitation.

PATIENTS

40 persons with low back pain from Rwanda's Northern Province were selected for the study. Among them, 20 received **physiotherapy services through the public health system** at Ruhengeri Referral and Teaching Hospital and Butaro Level 2 Hospital, and the other 20 used **digital rehabilitation with the Inclusion App**, accessed through CHWs.

Patient selection was based on the following criteria: completion of low back pain treatment within the past two months, residence in either Musanze or Burera districts, and willingness to participate in the survey. To protect confidentiality, no demographic or other medical history data were collected.

CARE PATHWAYS

The **two care pathways** for persons with low back pain are compared (Figure 1).

1. The standard physiotherapy pathway involves three nursing consultations at primary health centres before referral to a district hospital physician. The physician then refers some of these patients to the hospital's physiotherapy services. On average, patients are assumed to receive five 30-minute physiotherapy sessions. These physiotherapy services are often delayed and inaccessible to most patients using this pathway. On average, patients in the sample completed the pathway in 18 months.

2. The digital rehabilitation pathway begins with a consultation where a CHW introduces and trains clients to use the Inclusion App. CHWs also identify warning signs throughout the rehabilitation process that require immediate referral. Clients then use the application to do the recommended exercises independently. This approach allows more users to start guided low-back exercises sooner. On average, persons in the sample completed the digital rehabilitation pathway in 6 months.

COSTS

The costs of the two care pathways were analysed and compared from **the perspective of the healthcare payer**. These **direct costs** included reimbursement fees for consultations and X-rays, gross salary costs for medical personnel consultation time, CHW allowances, CHW training costs, and Inclusion App user fees. Costs related to pain medications, patients' out-of-pocket payments, and travel expenses were excluded. All costs are presented in Rwandan Francs (RWF) for 2024 and converted to USD at an exchange rate of 1 USD = 1,377 RWF as of December 31, 2024.

Figure 2: Direct healthcare payer costs per patient with low-back pain for the physiotherapy pathway and the digital rehabilitation pathway using the Inclusion App.

Figure 3: Health state outcomes before and after intervention for patients with low back pain following the physiotherapy pathway and the digital rehabilitation pathway using the Inclusion App. The vertical scale represents the EQ-5D-5L health state, where 0 indicates the worst possible health state and 1 represents perfect health.

Figure 4: QALYs gained per patient over an 18-month period for the physiotherapy pathway and the digital rehabilitation pathway using the Inclusion App. *The decline for the Inclusion App group is attributed to the assumed 33% one-year general recurrence rate after treatment.

The cost of the **physiotherapy** pathway includes reimbursement fees for consultations and a lumbosacral x-ray covered by the Community-Based Health Insurance and gross salary costs for the time spent on consultations, paid by the Ministry of Health [2,3]. These include 10-minute consultations by nurses and physicians, and 30-minute physiotherapy sessions provided by physiotherapists. The total cost of the standard pathway was **RWF 19,038 (US\$ 13.83) per patient** (Figure 2).

In the **digital rehabilitation** pathway, CHWs are unsalaried volunteers. However, during the pilot, they received a monthly transport allowance of RWF 10,000 (not to be included in the national implementation) and a monthly internet allowance of RWF 3,000. CHWs underwent half-day initial Inclusion App training, followed by a refresher training after one month. The allowance and training costs were distributed across all 6,089 users of the Inclusion App during the pilot. The cost of using the Inclusion App low back pain exercise programme was RWF 1,377 (US\$1.00) per user. The total cost of the digital rehabilitation pathway was **RWF 2,691 (US\$1.95) per user**. Compared to the standard physiotherapy pathway, using **the Inclusion App costs 7 times less per person** with low back pain.

EFFECTIVENESS

The effectiveness of both pathways was measured using the widely used **EQ-5D-5L quality of life questionnaire**, which assesses persons' health states across five dimensions: mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort, and anxiety/depression. Two retrospective measurements were conducted through phone interviews: the starting point, when clients first sought help for their low back pain from a nurse or a CHW, and the endpoint, which was either the last physiotherapy session or the time they completed the last exercise with the Inclusion App.

The results indicate that both pathways improved users' health states (Figure 3). However, **the digital rehabilitation pathway demonstrated substantially greater effectiveness** compared to the physiotherapy pathway. The digital rehabilitation pathway led to significantly better post-intervention health outcomes, highlighting its potential to deliver enhanced quality-of-life improvements for persons with low back pain.

QUALITY OF LIFE

The health state measurements were converted into **Quality-Adjusted Life Years (QALYs)**, accounting for the health states and the average durations of the treatment pathways: 18 months for physiotherapy and 6 months for the Inclusion App. Due to the shorter duration of the digital rehabilitation pathway, a constant health state with a 33% one-year general recurrence rate of low back pain was assumed for persons in the digital rehabilitation group during months 7 to 18 [4]. This approach ensures realistic and fair comparison between the two pathways over the same time frame.

Based on the 18-month timeline, the results demonstrate that the **Inclusion App pathway** achieved significantly higher quality of life impact, **with 1.38 QALYs gained per user**, compared to the **physiotherapy pathway**, which **0.47 QALYs gained per patient** (Figure 4). The digital rehabilitation pathway therefore gains nearly **3 times more QALYs per person** with low back pain than the standard physiotherapy pathway. These findings highlight the potential of the Inclusion App to produce improved health outcomes while utilising fewer healthcare resources. The results strongly support the value of digital rehabilitation in enhancing health outcomes and provide promising evidence for its wider adoption.

CONCLUSION

The Inclusion App demonstrates **improved health outcomes** for patients with low back pain in Rwanda compared to the standard physiotherapy services. This is likely due to faster and broader access to care through CHWs and digital rehabilitation services. Importantly, it is a **lower-cost** solution that also reduces the burden on healthcare personnel. These findings highlight the potential of digital rehabilitation to enhance patient outcomes while utilising fewer healthcare resources.

While the Inclusion App presents a **cost-effective alternative**, it is not intended to replace the standard physiotherapy services but to complement them. By providing patients with access to basic digital physiotherapy services, it can expand healthcare availability and reduce inequities, particularly in underserved areas. Integrating digital rehabilitation into primary care enables patients to begin treatment and recovery sooner, freeing up healthcare resources and therefore easing pressure on the healthcare system.

COST-EFFECTIVENESS

The Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) compares the cost and effectiveness of the physiotherapy and digital rehabilitation pathways. The digital rehabilitation is less expensive, with an incremental saving of RWF 16,347 per person, and it achieved better health outcomes, with incremental QALYs gained of 0.92 per person. Dividing the cost by the QALYs results in an ICER of RWF -17,850 per QALY (USD -12.96 per QALY). The negative ICER demonstrates that using **the Inclusion App is highly cost-effective compared to the standard physiotherapy pathway**, making it the preferred option for the Ministry of Health. It provides strong evidence that digital rehabilitation is an effective alternative for treating low back pain, delivering greater health benefits while reducing costs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1. Scale up digital rehabilitation solutions**, like the Inclusion App, through community health workers to improve access for persons with low back pain.
- 2. Assess the suitability and effectiveness of digital rehabilitation for other musculoskeletal disorders**, prioritising conditions based on prevalence and severity.
- 3. Explore reimbursement options for digital rehabilitation** under community-based health insurance, considering innovative payment models such as token-based approaches or performance-based financing.
- 4. Develop and implement training programmes for community health workers** to support the accelerated and sustained adoption of digital rehabilitation solutions.
- 5. Integrate digital rehabilitation tools with existing physiotherapy services**, positioning them as supportive and complementary solutions.

LIMITATIONS

These results provide an early indicator of the cost-effectiveness of digital rehabilitation services. However, the approach has some limitations. The sample size is small, and the retrospective measurement of health states is not optimal. Additionally, the analysis assumes a constant quality of life with a general recurrence rate beyond six months for persons in the digital rehabilitation pathway. Therefore, these findings should be considered approximate and exploratory indicators.

ETHICAL CLEARANCE

Ethical clearance for this study was granted by the Rwanda National Research Ethics Committee under the Ministry of Health (RNEC515/2024, issued on 22 August 2024).

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